

Sirtlar bilan bog'langan maksimal operatorlar
Maximal operators associated with singular surfaces
Usmanov Salim Eshimovich^{1,2}

¹ PhD, dotsent, o'qituvchi, Sharof Rashidov nomidagi Samarqand Davlat
Universiteti, u.salim@samdu.uz

² PhD, dotsent, o'qituvchi, Toshkent Kimyo xalqaro universiteti Samarqand
filiali
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17624562>

Annotatsiya: Mazkur ishda uch o'lchovli Evklid fazosida parametrik tenglamalar orqali berilgan singulyar sirtlar bilan bog'langan maksimal operatorlarning integrallanuvchi funksiyalar fazosida chegaralanganlik masalasi o'rganilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: gipersirt, maksimal operator, o'rtalashtirish operatori, singulyar sirt, regulyar nuqta, kasr-darajali qator.

Annotation: In this work, the problem of boundedness in the space of integrable functions of maximal operators associated with singular surfaces given by parametric equations in three dimensional Euclidean space is studied.

Key words: hypersurface, maximal operator, averaging operator, singular surface, regular point, fractional power series.

Kirish

Gipersirtlar bilan bog'langan maksimal operator quyidagicha aniqlanadi:

$$\mathcal{M}f(y) := \sup_{t>0} |A_t f(y)|, \quad (1)$$

bu yerda

$$A_t f(y) := \int_S f(y - tx) \psi(x) dS(x) \quad (2)$$

o'rtalashtirish operatori deb ataladi. $S \subset \mathbb{R}^{n+1}$ – gipersirt, ψ - kompakt tashuvchiga ega cheksiz marta differensiallanuvchi silliq nomanfiy funksiya, ya'ni $\psi \in C_0^\infty(\mathbb{R}^{n+1})$, $t > 0$ va $f \in C_0^\infty(\mathbb{R}^{n+1})$, $dS(x)$ – S dagi sirt o'lchovidir.

Agar $|f(x)|^p$ funksiya \mathbb{R}^{n+1} fazoda integrallanuvchi bo'lsa, u holda \mathbb{R}^{n+1} da aniqlangan f o'lchovli funksiyalar to'plamini $L^p := L^p(\mathbb{R}^{n+1})$ deb belgilaymiz.

Agar shunday musbat $C > 0$ soni mavjud bo'lib, har qanday $f \in C_0^\infty(\mathbb{R}^{n+1})$ uchun $\|\mathcal{M}f\|_{L^p} \leq C_p \|f\|_{L^p}$ tengsizlik (baho) bajarilsa, u holda $\mathcal{M}f$ maksimal operator L^p fazoda chegaralangan deyiladi.

Berilgan S gipersirt va berilgan $0 \leq \psi \in C_0^\infty(\mathbb{R}^{n+1})$ funksiya uchun mos keladigan maksimal operatorning chegaralanganlik ko'rsatkichi tabiiy ravishda ushbu munosabat bilan aniqlanadi:

$$p(S) := p_\psi(S) := \inf\{p: (1) \text{ operator } L^p \text{ da chegaralangan}\}.$$

Gipersirtlar bilan bog'liq maksimal operatorlar ko'plab olimlar tomonidan o'rganilgan. Birinchi marta 1976-yilda E.M.Stein isbotladiki, agar gipersirt birlik sfera bo'lsa, unga mos keladigan maksimal operator $p > \frac{n+1}{n}$ uchun $L^p(\mathbb{R}^{n+1})$ fazoda

chegaralangan, $1 \leq p \leq \frac{n+1}{n}$ uchun esa chegaralanmagan [1]. Keyinchalik E.M.Steinning isbotlash usullari qo'llanilmaydigan tekis holat uchun E.M.Stein teoremasining analogi J.Burgen tomonidan isbotlangan [2].

A.Greenleaf [3] isbotladiki, agar gipersirt \mathbb{R}^{n+1} ($n \geq 2$) da kelib chiqishiga nisbatan qat'iy qavariq va yulduzsimon bo'lsa (demak, koordinatadan chiqadigan har qanday nur gipersirtni bir nuqtada kesib o'tadi va gipersirtning Gauss egriligi musbat), u holda E.M.Stein teoremasining tasdiqlari to'g'ri bo'ladi. Bundan tashqari u ko'rsatganidek agar gipersirtning har bir nuqtasida kamida k ($k \geq 2$) ta bosh egriliklari nolga teng bo'lmasa, $p > \frac{k+1}{k}$ uchun maksimal operator L^p da chegaralangan. Murakkabroq holat $k = 1$ da integral operatorlarning lokal silliqigidan foydalangan holda, xuddi shunday natijani C.D.Sogge olgan [4]. Xususan, C.D.Sogge J.Burgen teoremasining yangi isbotini taqdim etdi.

Shuningdek, (1) maksimal operatorlarning chegaralanganligi M.Cowling, G.Mauceri, A.Nagel, A.Seeger, S.Wainger, A.Iosevich, E.Sawyer, M.Greenblatt ishlarida ham tadqiq qilingan [5]- [8].

I.A.Ikromov, M.Kempe va D.Müllerlar $p > h$ holatda bir jinsli gipersirtlar bilan bog'langan maksimal operatorlarning chegaralanganligini isbotladilar [9]-[10].

Undan tashqari, yoyiluvchan va singulyar sirtlar bilan bog'langan maksimal operatorlarning chegaralanganlik masalasi I.A.Ikromov va S.Usmanovlarning ishlarida ham o'rganilgan [11]-[12].

1-Ta'rif. $V \subseteq R_+^n$ ochiq, bog'langan to'lpam bo'lsin, bunda $0 \in \bar{V}$, $W \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n$ ochiq to'plam. f funksiya V to'plamda kasr darajali qator deyiladi, agar \bar{V} yopiq to'plam, N natural son va $\Phi_N^{-1}(W)$ to'plamda g haqiqiy analitik funksiya topilib, V to'plamda $f = g \circ \Phi_{1/N}$ tenglik o'rinli bo'lsa, bu yerda $\Phi_N: \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ akslantirish $\Phi_N(x) = (x_1^N, x_2^N, \dots, x_n^N)$ formula bilan berilgan [12].

Ushbu ishda quyidagi parametrik tenglamalar bilan berilgan \mathbb{R}^3 fazodagi sirtlarni qaraymiz:

$$\begin{aligned} x_1(u_1, u_2) &= u_1^{a_1} u_2^{a_2} g_1(u_1, u_2) \\ x_2(u_1, u_2) &= u_1^{b_1} u_2^{b_2} g_2(u_1, u_2) \\ x_3(u_1, u_2) &= r + u_1^{c_1} u_2^{c_2} g_3(u_1, u_2). \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Bu yerda r nol bo'lmagan haqiqiy son va $a_1, a_2, b_1, b_2, c_1, c_2$ darajalar manfiy bo'lmagan ratsional sonlar, $u_1 \geq 0, u_2 \geq 0, \{g_i(u_1, u_2)\}_{i=1}^3$ lar \mathbb{R}^2 da koordinatalar boshining yetarlicha kichik atrofida aniqlangan haqiqiy kasr darajali qatorlar.

Asosiy natija

Quyidagi belgilashlardan foydalanamiz:

$$B_1 = \begin{vmatrix} a_1 & b_1 \\ a_2 & b_2 \end{vmatrix}, \quad B_2 = \begin{vmatrix} b_1 & c_1 \\ b_2 & c_2 \end{vmatrix}, \quad B_3 = \begin{vmatrix} a_1 & c_1 \\ a_2 & c_2 \end{vmatrix}.$$

Ta'kidlash kerakki, agar $g_i(0,0) \neq 0$ va B_1, B_2, B_3 sonlardan kamida bittasi noldan farqli bo'lsa, u holda (2) sirtning $(0,0, r)$ nuqtasining yetarlicha kichik atrofida va koordinatalar boshi shu nuqtada bo'lgan koordinatalar sistemasining koordinata tekisliklaridan tashqarida yotadigan nuqtalari regulyar nuqtalaridir. (2) sirtning koordinatalar boshi $(0,0, r)$ nuqtada bo'lgan koordinatalar sistemasining koordinatalar tekisliklarida yotadigan nuqtalari uning singulyar nuqtalari bo'lishi mumkin [12].

(3) singulyar sirtlar bilan bog'langan (2) o'rtalashtirish operatorini quyidagicha aniqlaymiz:

$$A_t^\phi f(y) = \int_{\mathbb{R}_+^2} f(y_1 - tu_1^{a_1}u_2^{a_2}g_1(u_1, u_2), y_2 - tu_1^{b_1}u_2^{b_2}g_2(u_1, u_2), y_3 - t(r + u_1^{c_1}u_2^{c_2}g_3(u_1, u_2))) \cdot \psi_1(u_1, u_2) \sqrt{\phi(u_1, u_2)} du_1 du_2.$$

Bunda $\phi(u_1, u_2) = EG - F^2$ kasr darajali qator, E, F, G lar (3) sirtning birinchi kvadratik formasining koeffitsentlari, $f \in C_0^\infty(\mathbb{R}^3)$ va

$$\psi_1(u_1, u_2) = \psi(u_1^{a_1}u_2^{a_2}g_1(u_1, u_2), u_1^{b_1}u_2^{b_2}g_2(u_1, u_2), r + u_1^{c_1}u_2^{c_2}g_3(u_1, u_2)).$$

(1) ga ko'ra $A_t^\phi f$ operatorga mos maksimal operator quyidagiga teng:

$$\mathcal{M}^\phi f(y) := \sup_{t>0} |A_t^\phi f(y)|, \quad y \in \mathbb{R}^3.$$

$\mathcal{M}^\phi f$ maksimal operatorni (3) sirtning $(0,0,r)$ singulyar nuqtasining yetarlicha kichik atrofida o'rganamiz va bu operator $L^p(\mathbb{R}^3)$ fazoda bazi p ($p > 2$) larda chegaralanganligini va ba'zi p larda chegaralanmaganligini isbotlaymiz. Biz ushbu ishda $\mathcal{M}^\phi f$ maksimal operatorning chegaralanganlik ko'rsatkichi quyidagiga teng bo'lishi aniqlandi:

$$p(S) = \max \left\{ \frac{c_1}{a_1 + b_1}, \frac{c_2}{a_2 + b_2} \right\}.$$

Quyidagi teorema ishning asosiy natijasidir.

Teorema. Faraz qilaylik, $\{g_i(u_1, u_2)\}_{i=1}^3$ funksiyalar \mathbb{R}^2 fazoda koordinatalar boshining yetarlicha kichik atrofida aniqlangan haqiqiy kasr darajali qatorlar bo'lib, $g_i(0,0) \neq 0$ bo'lsin, hamda $B_1 B_2 B_3 \neq 0$ shart bajarilsin. U holda $(0,0,r)$ nuqtaning shunday kichik U atrofi topiladiki, ixtiyoriy $\psi_1 \in C_0^\infty(U)$ funksiya uchun $M^\phi f$ maksimal operator $p > \max\{p(S), 2\}$ bo'lganda $L^p(\mathbb{R}^3)$ fazoda chegaralangan bo'ladi. Bundan tashqari, agar yuqoridagi shartlar o'rinli va $\psi_1(0,0) > 0$, $p(S) > 2$ bo'lsa, u holda $M^\phi f$ maksimal operator $2 < p \leq p(S)$ bo'lganda $L^p(\mathbb{R}^3)$ fazoda chegaralanmagan bo'ladi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar

1. Stein E. M., Maximal functions. Spherical means, Proc.Nat. Acad. Sci. U.S.A., 73(7) (1976) 2174-2175.
2. Bourgain J., Averages in the plane convex curves and maximal operators, J.Anal. Math., 47 (1986) 69-85.
3. Greenleaf A. , Principal curvature and harmonic analysis, Indiana Univ. Math. J., 30(4) (1981) 519-537.
4. Sogge C.D., Maximal operators associated to hypersurfaces with one nonvanishing principal curvature. In Fourier analysis and partial differential equations, Stud. Adv. Math., pages 317-323.CRC, Boca Raton, FL, 1995.
5. Cowling M., and Mauceri G., Inequalities for some maximal functions. II. Trans. Amer. Math. Soc., 296(1):341-365, 1986.
6. Nagel A., Seeger A., and Wainger S., Averages over convex hypersurfaces. Amer. J. Math., 1993. 115. 4. P. 903-927.

7. Iosevich A., Maximal operators, associated to families of flat curves in the plane. *Duke Math. J.*, 76(2): 633-644, 1994.
8. Greenblatt M., L^p boundedness of maximal averages over hypersurfaces in R^3 . *Trans. Amer. Math. Soc.*, 2013. 365. P. 1875–1900.
9. Ikromov I.A., Kempe M., Müller D., Estimates for maximal functions associated to hypersurfaces in R^3 and related problems of harmonic analysis. *Acta Math.* 204 (2010), 151-271.
10. Ikromov I. A., Damped oscillatory integrals and maximal operators, *Mathematial Notes*, 78(6) (2005) 833-852.
11. Ikromov I.A., Usmanov S.E., On boundedness of maximal operators associated with hypersurfaces. *J Math Sci.* 264, (2022), 715-745.
12. Usmanov S. E., The Boundedness of Maximal Operators Associated with Singular Surfaces, *Russian Mathematics*, 65(6) (2021) 73-83.